

Challenges of Using E-Resources in Teaching and Learning of English Language in Public Secondary Schools in Kakamega County, Kenya

Dr. Mark W. Muvango ✉

*Research Fellow: Department of Educational Communication,
Technology and Curriculum Studies, Maseno University, Kenya*

Dr. Joash Kowino Obwana

*Lecturer, Department of Educational Communication,
Technology and Curriculum Studies, Maseno University, Kenya*

Dr. Ajuoga Milcah

Lecturer, Department of Education, St. Paul's University, Kenya

Abstract

Introduction of e-resources (electronic resources) in education posed great challenges to all stakeholders. However, they are indispensable tools that facilitated teaching and learning process. It was not clear whether teachers were using e-resources or not in the curriculum appropriately. The specific objective of the study was to: determine challenges of using e-resources in teaching and learning of English Language in public secondary schools in Kakamega County, Kenya. The study found out that inadequate internet infrastructure, lack of up-to-date computer software and hardware and insufficient internet/computer skills hampered the usage of e-resources in schools. Based on the findings, the study recommended that school administrators and other stakeholders should equip schools with adequate internet infrastructure and provide up-to-date computer software and hardware. More so, Ministry of Education (MOE) in conjunction with Kenya Institute Curriculum Development (KICD) should organise refresher courses on e-resources usage in order to sharpen teachers' and librarians' skills and knowledge. The study contributed to development of teacher of English in regard to technological innovation in the curriculum.

Keywords: *Challenges, use, e-resources.*

Abbreviation: PQ – Principal's Questionnaire, ETQ – English Teacher's Questionnaire, LQ – Learner's Questionnaire, KICD - Kenya Institute Curriculum Development, CD – ROM, ICT - Information Communication Technology, UNIX - Universal Network Information exchange, OPAC – Online Public Access Catalogue, MOE - Ministry of Education, KICD - Kenya Institute Curriculum Development

Suggested citation: Muvango, M.W., Obwana, J.K., & Milcah, A. (2025). Challenges of Using E-Resources in Teaching and Learning of English Language in Public Secondary Schools in Kakamega County, Kenya. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 3(1), 3-13. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2025.3(1).01

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Introduction

E-resources required computer access, whether through personal computer, mainframe or handheld mobile devices. They were accessed remotely via the internet or locally. Both online and offline resources (such as CD – ROMs) were in the scope of e-resources. Therefore, they also included materials that required use of a peripheral (for example, a CD – ROM player) attached to a computer (International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA), 2015). The research of Ruth (2014) indicated that despite good access to e-resources, their use were variable within and between departments. This showed lack of awareness of available e-resources in in the curriculum. She gathered data through use of Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) logs, questionnaire, group interviews and document analysis. Ruth's study targeted integration and use of Information Communication Technology (ICT) across a large secondary school in South West of England. Thus, single case study offered no basis for reliability or generality of the results (Krusenvik, 2014).

Furthermore, technology based education depended on speed of broad band, availability of web enabled and mobile compatible learning. This helped students to access e-content easily. The research determined barriers to utilizing ICT in education in India with a special focus on rural areas (Arnab & Dey, 2018). Contrarily, Sampath (2018) study evaluated digital divide in India and suggested that only 20.7% rural and 69.7% urban students used computer for academic purposes in India. The results revealed inadequate use of computers especially by rural students. This was because (Chetna, 2015) new technologies were scarcely used in Indian schools due to lack of e-skills. Chetna's study targeted ICT and quality education in Indian schools.

The research of Oberiri and Iyendo (2018) investigated the place of internet in academic research and learning of students. They used 250 undergraduate students in three selected universities within North – Eastern Nigeria. To gain an in – depth understanding of the perception of the students' views, a focus group was conducted with 18 students. In their research, students perceived that lack of digital readiness among staff and inefficient internet facility discouraged utilization of the internet in the institutions. The non use of internet decreased the scope of reading and reduced self-learning rate. They concentrated on impact of ICT application in library services provision in University of Dares Salaam. Similarly, Ngimi (2013) study noted that ICT was used to a limited extent in delivery of education. Challenges identified included lack of pedagogical competence of lecturers and inadequate infrastructure. Ngimi's study focused on opportunities and challenges for integrating ICTs in education delivery in the Institute of Continuing Education at the Open University, Tanzania. It employed multiple holistic case research design.

Nevertheless, Indembukhani (2021) study expressed that there was un-coordinated training on ICT integration and biasness in training of teachers in the curriculum. Thus, this limited use of technology in learning process. The study targeted integration of ICT and its contribution to the teaching of English in secondary schools in Kisumu County, Kenya. He used sample size of 43 teachers, one County Quality Assurance and Standards Officer (CQA&SO) and 10 principals. The study of Miima (2014) observed that Kakamega County was one of the largest counties with many public

schools equipped with e-resources. On the contrary, there was inadequate integration of ICTs in teaching and learning of Kiswahili language. Interestingly, the researcher did not come across any empirical evidence on integration of e-resources in teaching of English in the county. Therefore, it was from this background that the present study determined challenges for using e-resources in teaching and learning of English Language in public secondary schools in Kakamega County, Kenya. As a result, the following question was formulated to direct the study: What are the challenges of using e-resources in teaching and learning of English Language in public secondary schools in Kakamega County, Kenya?

Methodology

The research was guided by Bruner's Constructivism Theory (1990) and adopted descriptive survey design. The study population was 150 principals, 250 teachers of English and 10,000 Form Two students. Simple random sampling method used to select 108 principals, 152 teachers of English and 370 Form Two students. Research instruments included: questionnaires for principals, teachers and students, interview schedule and observation checklist for teachers. Face validity of research instruments was established by judgement of three experts in the Department of Educational Communication, Technology and Curriculum Studies. Reliability of instruments was established through pilot study. The computed coefficients of reliability were 0.85, 0.85 and 0.80 for questionnaires of principals, teachers and students respectively. Data was analysed through descriptive statistics included frequencies, means and percentages. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyse data.

Results and Discussions

Respondents established the barriers in access to and use of e-resources in teaching and learning of English language. Results summed up in Table 1.

Table 1. Barriers in Access to and Use of E-resources

n=152 Teachers of English

Barriers in Access to and Use of E-resources	Number of Teachers (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Lack of searching skills	111	73
Inability to access full-text articles	96	63
Shortage of staff	152	100
Lack of up – to date software and hardware	126	83
Inaccessibility of e-resources outside school premises due to Internet Protocol (IP) address limitations	132	87
Inadequate computers	111	73
Slow internet connectivity/network problems	123	81
Inadequate ICT Infrastructure		63
Virus attacks	96	63
Inadequate space for peer – teaching /instruction	138	91
Inadequate computer skills	96	63
Lack of administrative support in ICT	96	63
Poor students e-resource orientation	91	60
Frequent breakdown of ICT system	105	69
Erratic power supply	108	71

Lack of awareness of e-resources	96	63
Low band width	111	73
Insufficient information literacy skills	81	53
Inadequate retrieval skills	87	57

In Table 1, 100% teachers pointed that shortage of staff hindered accessibility and use of e-resources in education. Lack of searching skills (73%), inability to access full-text articles (63%), lack of up-to-date software and hardware (83%), inaccessibility of e-resources outside school premises due to IP address limitations (87%), inadequate computers (73%), slow internet connectivity/network problems (81%), inadequate ICT Infrastructure (63%), virus attacks (63%), inadequate space for peer – teaching /instruction (91%), inadequate computer skills (63%), lack of administrative support in ICT (63%), poor students e-resource orientation (60%), frequent breakdown of ICT system (69%), erratic power supply (71%), lack of awareness of e-resources (63%), low band width (73%), insufficient information literacy skills (53%) and inadequate retrieval skills (57%) were barriers in access to and utilization of e-resources in teaching and learning process.

The results showed inadequate technological facilities that were poorly maintained or insufficient up-to-date software and hardware. It was also indicated that low band width (slow internet connectivity/network problems) influenced negatively access to online – based information/web based Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) services. Therefore, school administrators must increase budget for internet subscription /bandwidth. Teachers were unable to download and print documents from the internet. It was important to be equipped with skills such as information retrieval skills, information literacy skills and computer skills as a strategy to promote access to and usage of e-resources in schools. These results concurred with Kelefa, Elia and Ndenje-Sichalwe (2017) study. Conversely, they conducted a research to compare use of electronic information resources in selected universities in Tanzania. They employed mixed methods research approach. SPSS and STATA used to analyse data.

Libraries were very crucial to teachers and learners in extending instructional services for instance orientation and training in use of library sources. Library e-resource hardware included computers, printers, scanners and photocopy machines. The different types of software tools for instance Operating Systems (OS) and networking systems such as windows, Universal Network Information exchange (UNIX) and Linus indicated the quality and performance of technology being used by the library. However, teachers and learners were not confident searching new databases in which no prior training was provided. Principal's Questionnaire (PQ) sought to find out challenges school libraries faced in regard to e-resources use in the curriculum. Results summed up in Table 2.

Table 2. Challenges School Libraries Encountered Regarding E-resources Use

n=108 Principals

Challenges School Libraries Encountered regarding E-resources Use	Number of Principals (<i>f</i>)	(%)
Inadequate funds/budget cuts	108	100
Limited e-resource search skills personnel	83	77
High cost of subscriptions fees	92	85

Lack of e-resources usage statistics	105	97
E-resource unskilled staff due to resignation	97	90
Lack of computers to access online e-resources	62	57

Table 2 revealed 100% principals faced inadequate funds/budget cuts thus hampering e-resources use in school libraries. Schools Libraries faced limited e-resource search skills personnel (77%), high cost of subscriptions fees (85%), lack of e-resources usage statistics (97%), e-resource unskilled staff due to resignation (90%) and lack of up-to-date computers to access online e-resources (57%). These were challenges which school libraries faced in regard to e-resources use in the curriculum.

Inadequate funds/budget cuts influenced subscriptions to relevant e-resources thus much needed e-content were inadequately accessed. Funds for procuring subscriptions were insufficient to purchase e-materials. Consequently, teachers and learners lost interest in accessing and using e-resources. Thus, schools must be provided enough funds to cater for purchasing licences from database owners and publishers.

Also, respondents suggested that schools libraries staff had inadequate: ICT education, collaboration and partnership. 97% schools lacked borrowing/returning statistics that showed numbers of teachers and learners using library facilities during specified period. Little data on photocopying, scanning and printing was available. This was the only method schools could use to measure e-resources usage in education.

Principals cited yearly budget cuts and regular fluctuation of inflation rates affected e-resources use in the curriculum. Budget cuts towards acquisition of e-resources contributed to fewer subscriptions to much needed e-materials in education. The results concurred with research of Lefuma (2017). However, she adopted the post – positivists’ paradigm and mixed methods that involved both qualitative and quantitative approaches. She determined access to and use of electronic information resources in the academic libraries of the Lesotho Library Consortium.

Furthermore, libraries had inadequate up – to – date computers. E-resources required computer mediation in order to access its content fast for teaching and learning process. It was pointed that library internet cafe was slow to send a letter or message or to open. Inadequate funds made schools unable to acquire up-to-date software and hardware to provide efficient and effective digital base information resources to teachers and learners. Lastly but not least, retention of trained library staff was major challenge thus influenced negatively access and use e-resources in the library. School administrators must motivate or appreciate them through regular benchmarking/ collaboration with others. Schools must initiate e-resource - based capacity building programmes for their library staffs. Budgets cuts and price increases confronted use of e-resources in the libraries. Decisions made by vendors and restrictive limited budgets hindered decision making process based on maintenance of e-resources in the curriculum. These results were in tandem with Yebowaah and Dzokotoe (2017) research. They determined awareness and use of electronic resources in university libraries. It was a case study and data was collected with aid of a questionnaire and analysed through use of library logistics regression model.

English Teacher’s Questionnaire (PQ) identified strategies used in schools to enhance access to and use of e-resources in the curriculum. Table 3 summed up the results.

Table 3. Strategies to Enhance Access and Use of E-resources*n*=152 Teachers of English

Strategies to Enhance Access and Use of E-resources	Number of Teachers (<i>f</i>)	Percentages (%)
Library orientation sessions	132	87
Information Literacy (IL)	141	93
Library displays	107	70
Institutions newsletters	137	90
Development of online user guidelines for accessing e-resources	96	63
Creation of user – friendly interfaces for easy access to online content	111	73
Provision of online information literacy platform	63	43

Table 3 depicted that library orientation sessions (87%), information literacy (93%), library displays (70%), institutions newsletters (90%), development of online user guidelines for accessing e-resources (63%), creation of user – friendly interfaces for easy access to online content (73%) and provision of online information literacy platform (43%) as strategies to use to enhance access to and use of e-resources in the curriculum. The study revealed that e-resources promotional materials be made available to teachers and learners for awareness of e-resources accessibility and usage. It was also noted that in – service training must be organised either by KICD, publishers, MOE or concerned library for teachers, library staff and even learners on e-resources access and usage. Further, at the beginning of each academic year, Form Ones must be organised into groups to attend demonstrations, discussions and deliberations on how to access and use e-resources in the curriculum.

Respondents established problems encountered during access of e-resources in the school libraries. Table 4 showed the results.

Table 4. Problems Encountered in E-resources Accessibility*n*=152 Teachers of English

Problems Encountered in E-resources Accessibility	Number of Teachers (<i>f</i>)	Percentages (%)
Slowness of downloads	141	93
Slow Personal Computers (PCs)	132	87
Vendor upgrades	152	100
Inadequate network	138	91
Insecurity	96	63
Insufficient training in e-resources use	81	53

In Table 4, slowness of downloads (93%), slow PCs (87%), vendor upgrades (100%), inadequate network (91%), insecurity (63%) and insufficient training in e-resources use (53%) hindered access of e-resources in the school libraries. This showed that teachers faced several challenges in accessing and use of e-resources in the library. In order to enhance access to and use of e-materials in the library; teachers, learners and library staff must work in concerted effort to ensure better services delivery. Adequate communication was required among all stakeholders in order to sensitize about e-resources access and use in education. More so, all stakeholders must be trained to improve information literacy for teachers and learners in schools. Also, teachers noted

that school libraries must install current technologies so as to remain relevant in information provision. Significantly, the access and use of internet technologies in libraries depended on sufficient funding for hardware, software purchase, maintenance contracts, upgrading of hardware and software systems and subscription costs to e-resources. The findings were supported by Masese, Omallah, Makwae and Moenga (2016) research. However, they targeted strategies to enhance access and use of e-resources by postgraduate students in selected university libraries in Kisii County, Kenya.

It was reported that respondents used Maintenance Wizard to check disk for problems, manage hard disk space efficiently, delete unnecessary files and make programs run faster. The Maintenance Wizard combined the functions of Scan Disk, Disk cleaning, Disk Defragmenter and compression Agent. It was noted that the schedule tasks could run on a regular basis.

ETQ revealed types of in-service training acquired by teachers relating to e-resource access and use in learning and teaching of English language. Results were summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Types of In-Service Training offered in the Curriculum

n=152 Teachers of English

Types of In-service Training offered in the Curriculum	Number of Teachers (<i>f</i>)	Percentages (%)
Workshops	90	59
Seminars	40	26
Refresher courses	87	57
Peer training/coaching	96	63

In Table 5, workshops (59%), seminars (26%), refresher courses (57%) and peer training/coaching (63%) were types of training acquired by teachers of English in relation to access and use of e-resources. Teachers attended fairly workshops, refresher courses and peer training/coaching unlike seminars in the curriculum. They enlarged and refined teacher's skills, knowledge and supported innovation in education. These training filled gaps left by pre-service training on use of e-resource in teaching and learning process. They noted that training on e-resources use attended was participatory and enriching in nature due to practical activities which were majorly utilized during training sessions. Generally, teachers were encouraged to use learner-centred activities supported with e-tools. However, respondents claimed that such training was: rarely conducted, costly and inconsistent thus few teachers attended them. Public schools were unable to send teachers and library staff for training regarding e-resources use in education due to little investment in staff development courses. E-resources knowledge acquired from training assisted in planning and implementation of innovations in schools. These workshops, seminars and refreshers courses were offered by KICD and MOE.

Learner's Questionnaire (LQ) identified problems that hindered access and use of e-resources in learning of English language. Results were summed up in Table 6.

Table 6. Problems Learners Faced in E-resource Accessibility and Usage*n*=370 Learners

Problems Learners faced in E-resource Accessibility and Usage	Number of Teachers (<i>f</i>)	Percentages (%)
Limited access to e-resources	222	60
Use of E-resources was time consuming	148	40
E-resources use was a waste of time	85	23
Inadequate e-resources knowledge to effectively use them	185	50
Lack of skilled man power	211	57
Uncooperative library staff to facilitate e-resources access and use	181	49
Power and equipment failure	211	57
Low network	233	63
Poor maintenance of equipment	241	65
Inadequate computer terminals	226	61
Regulatory restriction of communication technologies	189	51
Unreliable technologies	233	63

In Table 6, majority of learners revealed that use of e-resources was neither a waste of time nor time consuming in the curriculum. Power and equipment failure (57%), low network (63%), poor maintenance of equipment (61%) and inadequate computer terminals (61%) obstructed e-resources accessibility and usage in learning of English language. Most schools did not have budgets for e-resources thus they relied on donors/external funding to implement e-resources accessibility and usage. Thus, schools were unable to pay for adequate bandwidth. High cost of connectivity caused inadequacy in use of e-resources in education.

Furthermore, learners pointed that regulatory restriction of communication technologies (51%), unreliable technologies (63%), uncooperative library staff to facilitate e-resources access and use (49%), lack of skilled man power (57%), inadequate e-resources knowledge to effectively use them (50%) and limited access to e-resources (60%) hampered accessibility and use of e-resources in learning of English language. The results revealed that access to adequate e-resources was still a problem for most schools. Data base required user name and passwords to use them. However, restrictions were necessary because of licence agreement with vendors. Hadi and Zeinab (2012) results were in line with this study. However, they used stratified sampling to select 30 high school English (18 males and 12 females) randomly from all the educational districts in the city of Isfahan, Iran, to respond to the questionnaire.

PQ found out from principals ways of improving use of e-resources in the curriculum. Results were summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Ways of Improving Use of E-Resources*n*=108 Principals

Ways of Improving use of E-resources	Number of Teachers (<i>f</i>)	Percentages (%)
Regular refresher courses	108	100
Provision of enough staff	108	100
E-resources adequate budget allocation	108	100
Subsidized subscription fee	97	90

Regular supply of up-to-date computers	95	88
Improved internet connectivity	98	91
Protection of equipment from virus attacks	92	85
Creation of enough space for peer-training/coaching	87	81

Table 7, 100% principals suggested that with regular refresher courses, provision of enough staff and e-resources adequate budget allocation would improve use of e-resources in the curriculum. Others cited subsidized subscription fee (90%), regular supply of up-to-date computers (88%), improved internet connectivity (91%), protection of equipment from virus attacks (85%) and creation of enough space for peer training/coaching (81%) would improve utilization of e-resources in education.

The schools administrators and other stakeholders such as Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) and Ministry of Education (MOE) must prepare for aggressive training programmes targeting teachers. However, training on access to and use of e-resources must start with schools library staff due to inadequate digital skills barred teachers and learners from information search and retrieval in the school library.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

E-resources were inadequately used due to insufficient internet infrastructure and lack of up-to-date computer software and hardware in schools. More so, teachers and library staff lacked internet and computer skills for search, retrieval and storage of e-content.

Policy Recommendations

Administrators and other stakeholders should equip schools with adequate internet facility and provide up-to-date computer software and hardware. More so, MOE in conjunction with KICD should organise for refresher courses on e-resources usage for teachers and even library staff in the curriculum.

References

- Arnab, K., & Dey, K. N. (2018). Barriers to utilizing ICT in education in India with a special focus on rural areas. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Reviews*, 7(2), 341–359.
- Bruner, J. (1990). *Acts of meaning*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Chetna, P. (2015). ICT and quality education in Indian schools. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*, 3(4), 603–605.
- Habiba, U., & Salma, C. (2012). Use of e-resources and its impact: A study of Dhaka University library users. *The Eastern Librarian*, 23(1), 74–90.
- Hadi, S., & Zenaib, S. (2012). Challenges for using ICT in education: Teacher's insight. *International Journal of Education, e-Business, e-Management and e-Learning*, 2(1), 40–43.

- Halima, E. S. (2011). The use and impact of electronic resources at the University of Lagos. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, (e-journal). Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/472>
- Indembukhani, K. (2021). Integration of ICT and its contribution to the teaching of English in secondary schools in Kisumu County, Kenya. Retrieved from <https://repository.maseno.ac.ke/handle/123456789/4012>
- International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA). (2015). Freedom of access to information and freedom of expression: Libraries and intellectual freedom. Retrieved from <http://www.ifla.org/faife/present.htm>
- Kelefa, M., Elia, E., & Ndenje-Sichalwe, E. (2017). Utilization of e-resources to support teaching and research in higher learning institutions, Tanzania. *University of Dar es Salaam Library Journal*, 12(2), 98–123.
- Kihoza, P., Zlotnikova, I., Bada, J., & Khamisi, K. (2016). Classroom ICT integration in Tanzania: Opportunities and challenges from the perspectives of TPACK and SAMR models. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT)*, 12(1), 107–128.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30, 607–610.
- Krusenvik, L. (2014). Using case studies as a scientific method: Advantages and disadvantages. Halmstad University, Halmstad, Sweden. Retrieved from <https://www.diva-portal.org>
- Lefuma, S. (2017). Access to and use of electronic information resources in the academic libraries of the Lesotho Library Consortium. (Doctoral dissertation, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa).
- Masese, M. J., Omallah, G. B., Makwae, N. E., & Moenga, N. E. (2016). Strategies to enhance access and use of e-resources by postgraduate students in selected university libraries in Kisii County, Kenya. *International Journal of Academic Library and Information Science*, 4(8), 203–207.
- Microsoft Corporation. (1998). *Getting started: Microsoft Windows 98*. New York: Microsoft Corporation.
- Miima, F. A. (2014). Integration of ICTs in teaching and learning of Kiswahili language in public secondary schools in Kakamega County, Kenya. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Kenyatta University).
- Nawe, J., & Kiondo, E. (2005). The impact of ICT application in library services provision on the core mission of University of Dar es Salaam.
- Ngimi, H. M. (2013). Opportunities and challenges for integrating ICTs in education delivery in the Institute of Continuing Education at the Open University of Tanzania. (Master's thesis, Open University of Tanzania).
- Oberiri, D. A., & Iyendo, O. T. (2018). University students' usage of the internet resources for research and learning: Forms of access and perceptions of utility. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
- Ruth, M. F. (2014). The integration and use of ICT across the secondary school. (Doctoral dissertation, Cardiff University).

Sampath, K. (2018). The digital divide in India: Use and non-use of ICT by rural and urban students. *World Journal of Science, Technology and Sustainable Development*, 15(2), 156–168. <https://doi.org/10.1108/WJSTSD-07-2017-0021>

Vinod, K. S. (2015). Use of e-resources and services by users at Indian Institute of Management Kozhikode. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 4(11), 25–41.

Yebowaah, F., & Dzokotoe, D. F. (2017). Awareness and use of electronic resources in university libraries: A case study of University for Development Studies Library. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net>

